

Heterocyclic Compounds from β -Diketones. Part III. 2-Sulphanilamidoazoacetyl- and -benzoyl-acetones and their Cyclisation

Anil Prakash and I. R. Gambhir

2-Sulphanilamidoazoacetylacetones and 2-sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetones have been obtained by the reaction of the diazotised solution of sulphanilamides with acetylacetone and benzoylacetone respectively. Their behaviours with hydrazine, semicarbazide, and hydroxylamine have been studied and cyclic compounds, such as pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives, prepared.

The diazonium chlorides of 2-sulphanilamides readily couple with β -keto-esters, such as ethyl acetoacetate¹. It has now been observed that these also couple with β -diketones, such as acetylacetone and benzoylacetone, to yield 2-sulphanilamidoazo ketones. Thus the diazotised solutions of sulphanilamides with acetylacetone yield 2-sulphanilamidoazoacetylacetone (I) and with benzoylacetone, 2-sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetone (II).

(I): R = Me; R' = H.

(II): R = Ph; R' = H.

(R' = H, COMe, thiazole, pyridine, pyrimidine nuclei etc.)

These 2-sulphanilamidoazo ketones react with hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide acetate, phenylhydrazine, *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine, and hydroxylamine acetate to form pyrazole, pyrazole-1-amide, phenylpyrazole, sulphamylphenylpyrazole, and isoxazole derivatives. Thus 2-sulphanilamidoazoacetylacetone (I) yields with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (Ia); with semicarbazide acetate in ethanol, 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo) pyrazole-1-amide (Ib); with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid, 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (Ic); with *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine in acetic acid, 1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (III); with hydroxylamine acetate in ethanol, 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)isoxazole (IV).

(Ia): R = Me; X = H.

(IIa): R = Ph; X = H.

(Ib): R = Me; X = CONH₂.

(IIb): R = Ph; X = CONH₂.

(Ic): R = Me; X = Ph.

(IIc): R = X = Ph.

(R₁ = -N:N·C₆H₄SO₂NHR')

2-Sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetone (II) can, however, yield two pyrazole derivatives according as one or the other carbonyl group reacts; but under the usual experimental conditions, only one has been isolated. Since in benzoylacetone the group adjacent to the methyl group first reacts to form a hydrazone, which cyclises to a pyrazole, compound (II) too is expected to behave in the same way. Thus compound (II) yields with hydrazine hydrate 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole (IIa); with semicarbazide acetate, 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole-1-amide (IIb); with phenylhydrazine, 1,5-diphenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo) pyrazole (IIc); with *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine, 1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole (VI); with hydroxylamine acetate, 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylisoxazole (VII).

The isoxazole (IV), when heated with *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine in acetic acid, is converted into the phenylpyrazole derivative (III). The structure of the latter also follows from its formation from β -diketones, when it is first treated with *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine, and then coupling the product formed (V) with the diazonium chloride of sulphanilamide. A similar behaviour is shown by isoxazole (VII).

The sulphanilamidoazo ketones containing thiazole, pyridine, and pyrimidine nuclei and their cyclisation products are likely to be effective antibacterials.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Sulphanilamidoazoacetylacetone (I).—An ice-cooled solution of acetylacetone (1.0 g.), ethanol (25 ml), water (25 ml), and sodium acetate (60 g.) were vigorously shaken with the diazotised solution of sulphanilamide (1.8 g.). A pale yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in 80% yield of the product (I) in golden yellow prisms, m.p. 215°. (Found: S, 11.22. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 11.30%). 2,4-DNP of compound (I) was obtained as orange-red plates, m.p. 280°. (Found: S, 6.73. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 6.91%).

2-Sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetone (II) was prepared as above, using benzoylacetone (1.6 g.), ethanol (25 ml), water (20 ml) and sodium acetate (50 g.). Recrystallisation from acetic acid furnished 76% of the product (II) in yellow needles, m.p. 217°. (Found: S, 9.19. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 9.27%). 2,4-DNP of compound (II) was obtained as orange-plates, m.p. 285°. (Found: S, 5.89. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3\text{S}$ requires S, 6.09%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few more 2-sulphanilamidoazoacetylacetones and 2-sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetones have been prepared and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	2-Sulphanil- amid- azoacetone.	M.P.	Yield.	Sulphur.		2,4- DNP M.P.	2-Sulphanilamidoazobenzoylacetones.				
				Found.	Reqd.		M.P.	Yield.	%Sulphur.		2,4- DNP M.P.
				Found.	Reqd.		M.P.	Yield.	Found.	Reqd.	
1	-acetamido-	209°	80 %	9.78	9.84	240°	183°	75 %	8.21	8.26	230°
2	-thiazole-	241°	78	17.40	17.48	269°	249°	75	14.80	14.95	294°
3	-methyl- thiazole-	252°	78	16.73	16.84	294°	257°	74	14.40	14.48	301°
4	-pyridine-	205°	77	8.81	8.88	261°	219°	72	7.49	7.58	265°
5	-pyrimidine-	173°	78	8.78	8.86	237°	177°	72	7.45	7.56	244°
6	-4-methyl- pyrimidine-	180°	76	8.47	8.53	242°	197°	70	7.22	7.32	250°
7	-4,6-dimethyl- pyrimidine-	103°	76	8.45	8.23	250°	212°	70	7.00	7.09	283°
8	-benzene-	178°	74	8.84	8.01	265°	154°	71	7.53	7.60	271°

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (Ia).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.), glacial acetic acid (10 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (1.0 g.) were heated for 3 hr. On cooling, a yellow precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 68% yield of pyrazole (Ia) as yellow needles, m.p. 253°. (Found: S, 11.40. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 11.47%).

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole (IIa) was prepared similarly as above from hydrazine hydrate and compound (II). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 61% yield in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 280°. (Found: S, 9.29. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 9.38%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-pyrazoles and 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazoles have been prepared and are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo) pyrazoles.					3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazoles.					
No.*	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1	253°	68 %	$C_{13}H_{15}O_2N_3S$	9.88	9.96	246°	61%	$C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_3S$	8.28	8.35
2	245°	68	$C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_6S_2$	17.61	17.58	259°	58	$C_{19}H_{16}O_2N_6S_2$	15.00	15.09
3	250°	67	$C_{15}H_{16}O_2N_6S_2$	16.94	17.02	267°	58	$C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_6S_2$	14.53	14.61
4	244°	67	$C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_6S$	8.92	8.98	240°	60	$C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_6S$	7.59	7.65
5	248°	64	$C_{15}H_{15}O_2N_7S$	8.80	8.98	242°	60	$C_{20}H_{17}O_2N_7S$	7.52	7.63
6	250°	64	$C_{16}H_{17}O_2N_7S$	8.55	8.62	234°	60	$C_{21}H_{19}O_2N_7S$	7.30	7.39
7	254°	64	$C_{17}H_{19}O_2N_7S$	8.26	8.31	275°	57	$C_{22}H_{21}O_2N_7S$	7.09	7.16
8	220°	69	$C_{17}H_{17}O_2N_5S$	8.96	0.01	225°	60	$C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_5S$	7.60	7.67

*As recorded in Table I.

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole-1-amide (Ib).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.0 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hr. The precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 68% yield as pale yellow needles, m.p. 241°. (Found: S, 9.81. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3N_6S$ requires S, 9.93%).

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole-1-amide (IIb) was prepared from semicarbazide hydrochloride and compound (II). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 64% yield as yellow prisms, m.p. 245°. (Found: S, 8.21. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_6S$ requires S, 8.33%).

By adopting a similar procedure, a few 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-pyrazole-1-amides and 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole-1-amides have been prepared and are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

*No.	M.P.	Yield.	3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole-1-amides.		3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole-1-amides.		*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.		% Sulphur.	
			Formula.	% S	Formula.	% S				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	255°	68 %	$C_{14}H_{16}O_4N_6S$	8.72	8.79	250°	64 %	$C_{19}H_{18}O_4N_6S$	7.43	7.51			
2	268°	65	$C_{15}H_{15}O_3N_7S_2$	15.71	15.80	250°	63	$C_{20}H_{17}O_3N_7S_2$	13.64	13.70			
3	274°	65	$C_{16}H_{17}O_3N_7S_2$	15.19	15.27	269°	63	$C_{21}H_{19}O_3N_7S_2$	13.22	13.30			
4	274°	66	$C_{17}H_{17}O_3N_7S_2$	7.94	8.02	250°	60	$C_{22}H_{19}O_3N_7S$	6.83	6.94			
5	272°	62	$C_{16}H_{16}O_3N_8S$	7.90	8.00	247°	58	$C_{21}H_{18}O_3N_8S$	6.85	6.92			
6	280°	62	$C_{17}H_{18}O_3N_8S$	7.62	7.73	254°	58	$C_{22}H_{20}O_3N_8S$	6.66	6.72			
7	295°	60	$C_{18}H_{20}O_3N_8S$	7.34	7.47	263°	58	$C_{23}H_{22}O_3N_8S$	6.47	6.53			
8	241°	64	$C_{18}H_{19}O_3N_6S$	8.00	8.04	237°	60	$C_{23}H_{20}O_3N_6S$	6.85	6.95			

*As recorded in Table I.

1-Phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (Ic).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in glacial acetic acid (8 ml) and phenylhydrazine (1.0 g.) were heated for 2 hr. and then cooled. The solid separating was recrystallised from acetic acid in 75% yield as orange needles, m.p. 243°. (Found: S, 8.89. $C_{17}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 9.01%).

1,5-Diphenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (IIc) was prepared from phenylhydrazine and compound (II). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 71% yield as orange-red plates, m.p. 246°. (Found: S, 7.60. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 7.67%).

By a similar procedure as above, a few 1-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)- and 1,5-diphenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-pyrazoles were prepared. These are recorded in Table IV.

1-(p-Sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazole (III) was prepared from *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine and compound (I). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 70% yield as orange needles, m.p. 245°. (Found: S, 14.64. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4N_6S$ requires S, 14.74%).

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)isoxazole (IV).—A solution of compound (I) (2.8 g.) in ethanol (10 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g.), and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) were refluxed for 2 hr. On adding water a precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from acetic acid yielded 60% of the product (IV) in lemon-yellow needles, m.p. 237°. (Found: S, 11.31. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3N_4S$ requires S, 11.42%).

TABLE IV

1-Phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-pyrazoles.					1,5-Diphenyl-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-pyrazoles.				
*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur. Found. Reqd.	
1	253°	75 %	$C_{19}H_{19}O_2N_3S$	8.00 8.06	255°	70 %	$C_{24}H_{21}O_3N_3S$	6.90	6.97
2	270°	75	$C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_6S_2$	11.54 11.61	200°	68	$C_{25}H_{20}O_2N_6S_2$	12.71	12.80
3	281°	74	$C_{21}H_{20}O_2N_6S_2$	14.08 14.16	208°	68	$C_{26}H_{22}O_2N_6S_2$	12.34	12.45
4	260°	72	$C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_6S$	7.31 7.40	241°	65	$C_{27}H_{22}O_2N_6S$	6.39	6.47
5	225°	72	$C_{21}H_{19}O_2N_7S$	7.30 7.39	241°	63	$C_{26}H_{21}O_2N_7S$	6.37	6.46
6	240°	70	$C_{22}H_{21}O_2N_7S$	7.04 7.16	245°	63	$C_{27}H_{23}O_2N_7S$	6.20	6.28
7	258°	70	$C_{23}H_{23}O_2N_7S$	6.82 6.94	264°	60	$C_{28}H_{25}O_2N_7S$	6.02	6.12
8	214°	71	$C_{23}H_{21}O_2N_5S$	7.35 7.42	259°	64	$C_{28}H_{23}O_2N_5S$	6.42	6.49

*As recorded in Table I.

1-(*p*-Sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-dimethylpyrazole (V).—The mixture of acetylacetone (1.0 g.), *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine (1.8 g.), and sodium acetate (1.0 g.) in water (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. on a water bath. A colorless precipitate separating was recrystallised from ethanol in 76% yield as colorless needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: S, 12.62. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 12.75%).

1-(*p*-Sulphamylphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazole (VI) was prepared from sulphamylphenylhydrazine and compound (II). It was recrystallised from ethanol in 65% yield as orange-red plates, m.p. 255°. (Found: S, 12.78. $C_{24}H_{20}O_4N_6S_2$ requires S, 12.90%).

3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylisoxazole (VII) was prepared from hydroxylamine hydrochloride and compound (II). Recrystallisation from acetic acid furnished 57% of the product (VII) as yellow needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: S, 9.22. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_4S$ requires S, 9.35%).

1-(*p*-Sulphamylphenyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (VIII) was prepared from benzoylacetone and *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine. It was recrystallised from ethanol in 70% yield as colorless needles, m.p. 205°. (Found: S, 10.14. $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires S, 10.22%).

By a similar procedure as above, a few 1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazoles, 1-(*p*-sulphamylphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazoles, 3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)isoxazoles, and 3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylisoxazoles were prepared. These are recorded in Tables V and VI.

TABLE V

1-(<i>p</i> -Sulphamylphenyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)pyrazoles.					1-(<i>p</i> -Sulphamylphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylpyrazoles.					
*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1	235°	70 %	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	13.37	13.44	260°	65 %	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₆ S ₂	11.80	11.89
2	300°	69	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₇ S ₃	18.51	18.57	300°	64	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₇ S ₃	16.50	16.58
3	312°	69	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₇ S ₃	18.00	18.08	320°	64	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₃	16.08	16.18
4	251°	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	12.43	12.52	259°	60	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₇ S ₂	11.10	11.17
5	246°	64	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	12.43	12.50	261°	60	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ C ₄ N ₈ S ₂	11.04	11.15
6	254°	64	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	12.08	12.16	260°	60	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	10.80	10.88
7	268°	62	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	11.74	11.85	269°	57	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₈ S ₂	10.53	10.63
8	235°	62	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	12.44	12.55	261°	60	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆ S ₂	11.10	11.10

*As recorded in Table I.

TABLE VI

3,5-Dimethyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)isoxazoles.					3-Methyl-4-(2'-sulphanilamidoazo)-5-phenylisoxazoles.					
*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Sulphur.	
				Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1	260°	60 %	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ S	9.85	9.93	230°	57 %	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ S	8.28	8.33
2	289°	58	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	17.57	17.63	238°	54	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	14.93	15.06
3	301°	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	16.89	16.97	247°	54	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₅ S ₂	14.48	14.57
4	258°	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₅ S	8.84	8.96	230°	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₅ S	7.53	7.63
5	234°	54	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	8.82	8.93	250°	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆ S	7.50	7.61
6	259°	54	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₆ S	8.53	8.60	261°	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	7.24	7.37
7	268°	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₆ S	8.21	8.29	276°	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₆ S	7.05	7.14
8	271°	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ S	8.90	8.98	276°	53	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₄ S	7.80	7.85

*As recorded in Table I.

Grateful acknowledgements are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for the award of a research scholarship to one of the authors (A.P.).